

A Study of Countable, Uncountable, Bounded and Compact Sets on the Metric Spaces

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Abstract

In this paper some definitions of countable set, uncountable set and metric space are first investigated. Then the properties of the countable set and uncountable set are studied. After that, the results of the metric spaces on a real line R , R^2 and the Euclidean space R^k are investigated. Moreover, some concepts of bounded set and compact set on the metric space are presented.

Introduction

In this paper, various notions of size associated to subsets of R will be investigated. Here on specific definitions and theorems of interest are concentrated on. A countable set is a set with the same cardinality (number of elements) as some subset of the set of natural numbers. An uncountable set (or uncountably infinite set) is an infinite set that contains too many elements to be countable. Here the elements of the theory of metric spaces; a metric space is simply a nonempty set X such that to each $x, y \in X$ there corresponds a non-negative number called the distance between x and y are given. In order to make the theory sufficiently rich, this distance is supposed to have certain properties, such as symmetry and the triangle inequality, that are familiar from Euclidean geometry.

1. Countable Set and Uncountable Set

In this section, the definitions of countable set and uncountable set are introduced. Then some properties of countable set and uncountable set will be discussed.

1.1 Definition. Let A and B be nonempty sets. If there exists a 1-1 mapping of A onto B , we can say that A and B can be put in 1-1 correspondence or that A and B have the same cardinal number or, briefly, $A \sim B$.

This relation clearly has the following properties:

- (i) Reflexive : $A \sim B$,
- (ii) Symmetric : If $A \sim B$, then $B \sim A$,
- (iii) Transitive : If $A \sim B$ and $B \sim C$ then $A \sim C$.

Any relation with these three properties is called an *equivalent relation*.

1.2 Definitions. For any positive integer n , let J_n be the set whose elements are the integers $1, 2, 3, \dots, n$; let J be the set consisting of all positive integers.

For any set A ,

- (a) A is *finite* if $A \sim J_n$ for some n .
- (b) A is *infinite* if A is not finite.
- (c) A is *countable* if $A \sim J$.
- (d) A is *uncountable* if A is neither finite nor countable.

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(e) A is **at most countable** if A is finite or countable.

1.3 Definitions. Let J be the set of all positive integers. Suppose f is a mapping from A to J and f is defined by $f(n) = x_n$, for $n \in J$, it is customary to denote the sequence f by the symbol $\{x_n\}$, or sometimes by $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots$. The value of f , that is, the elements x_n , are called the **terms of sequence**. If A is a set and if $x_n \in A$ for all $n \in J$, then $\{x_n\}$ is said to be a **sequence in A** , or a **sequence of elements of A** .

1.4 Remarks. (i) The terms $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots$ of a sequence need not be distinct.

(ii) Every countable set as the range in a sequence of distinct terms.

(iii) The elements of any countable set can be “arranged in a sequence”.

1.5 Theorem. Every infinite subset of a countable set is countable.

Proof. Let A be a countable set and E be infinite of A .

Suppose $E \subseteq A$.

Since A is countable set, we may arrange the elements of A in a sequence $\{x_n\}$ of distinct terms.

$$A = \{x_n\}, n \in J.$$

Construct a sequence $\{n_k\}$ as follows.

Let n_1 be the smallest positive integer such that $x_{n_1} \in E$.

Having chosen $n_1, \dots, n_{k-1}$ ($k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$).

Let n_k be the smallest integer greater than n_{k-1} such that $x_{n_k} \in E$.

By induction, we get $\{x_{n_k}\}, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ such that $x_{n_k} \in E$.

Define a mapping $f: J \rightarrow E$ by $f(k) = x_{n_k}$, $k \in J$ where J is the set of all positive integers.

Then f is 1-1 and onto.

So $J \sim E$.

Thus $E \sim J$.

Therefore E is countable.

1.6 Theorem. Let $\{E_n\}, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ be a sequence of countable sets and put $S = \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} E_n$. Then S is countable.

Proof. Since $E_n, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ are countable, we can arrange the elements of E_n in a sequence $\{x_{nk}\}, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ for each n .

Consider the following infinite array in which the elements of E_n from the n^{th} row

The array contains all elements of S and these elements can be arranged in a sequence.

$$x_{11}, x_{21}, x_{12}, x_{31}, x_{22}, x_{13}, x_{41}, x_{32}, x_{23}, x_{14}, \dots$$

If any two of the set E_n have common elements, these will appear more than once in the above sequence.

Hence there is a subset T of the set of all positive integers such that $S \subseteq T$.

Since the set of all positive integers is countable, T is at most countable.

Thus S is at most countable.

Since $E_1 \cap S$, and E_1 is infinite, S is infinite, and thus countable. $\square$

1.7 Corollary. Let A be an at most countable set, and for every $\alpha \in A$, let B_α be at most countable. Then $T = \bigcup_{\alpha \in A} B_\alpha$ is at most countable.

Proof. Since A is at most countable, A may be finite or countable.

Thus T is equivalent to a subset of $\bigcup_{\alpha=1}^{\aleph} B_\alpha$.

Put $S = \bigcup_{\alpha=1}^{\aleph} B_\alpha$.

Since B_α is at most countable, it follows from Theorem 1.7 that S is countable.

Hence T is at most countable.

1.8 Theorem. Let A be a countable set, and let B_n be the set of n -tuples $(a_1, \dots, a_n)$, where $a_k \in A$ ($k = 1, \dots, n$), and the elements $a_1, \dots, a_n$ need not be distinct. Then B_n is countable.

Proof. Let $B_n = \{(a_1, \dots, a_n) \mid a_k \in A, k = 1, \dots, n\}$.

Then $B_1 = A$, so B_1 is countable.

Suppose B_{n-1} is countable. ($n = 2, 3, 4, \dots$)

$$B_n = \{(b, a) \mid b \in B_{n-1}, a \in A\}.$$

For every fixed b , let $A_b = \{(b, a) \mid a \in A\}$.

Then $A_b \subseteq A$.

Thus A_b is countable.

Hence $B_n = \bigcup_{b \in B_{n-1}} A_b$ is countable, since B_n is the union of a countable set of countable sets. $\square$

1.9 Corollary. The set of all rational numbers is countable.

Proof. Let Q be the set of rational numbers.

Let Z be the set of all integers.

Then $Q = \left\{ \frac{b}{a} \mid a, b \in Z, a \neq 0 \right\}$.

Let $S = \{(b, a) \mid a, b \in Z, a \neq 0\}$.

There is one to one correspondence between Q and S .

So $Q \sim S$.

Since Z is countable, S is countable.

Hence Q is countable. $\square$

1.10 Corollary. The set of all irrational real numbers is uncountable.

Proof. Let Q be the set of rational numbers and I be the set of irrational numbers.

Then $Q \cup I = \mathbb{R}$ the set of real numbers.

Suppose I is countable set.

Since Q is countable set, $Q \cup I = \mathbb{R}$ is countable.

But $\mathbb{R}$ is uncountable.

It is a contradiction.

So I is uncountable.

Therefore the set of all irrational real numbers is uncountable. $\square$

1.11 Theorem. Let A be the set of all sequences whose elements are the digit 0 and 1. This set A is uncountable.

Proof. The elements of A are sequences like $1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, \dots$.

Let E be a countable subset of A and let E consists of the sequences $s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots$.

Construct a sequence s as follows:

If the n^{th} digit in s_n is 1, let the n^{th} digit of s be 0; and vice versa.

Then the sequence s differs from every member of E in at least one place.

Hence $s \notin E$. But $s \in A$.

Thus E is a proper subset of A .

This show that every countable subset of A is a proper subset of A .

If A is countable, A will be a proper subset of A , which is impossible.

Hence A is uncountable. $\square$

2. Metric Spaces

In this section we will first give the definition of a metric space and then we will discuss some results on the metric space. Moreover, we investigate some concepts of bounded set and compact set on the metric space.

2.1 Definitions. A set X , whose elements we shall call *points*, is said to be a *metric space* if with any two points p and q of X there is associated a real number $d(p, q)$, called the *distance* from p to q ; such that

$$(i) \quad d(p, q) > 0 \text{ if } p \neq q; d(p, p) = 0 \text{ if } p = q$$

$$(ii) \quad d(p, q) = d(q, p)$$

$$(iii) \quad d(p, q) \leq d(p, r) + d(r, q), \text{ for any } r \in X.$$

Any function with these three properties is called a *distance function*, or a *metric*.

2.2 Example. Consider $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^2$ if $d(x, y) = |x_1 - y_1| + |x_2 - y_2|$, where

$$x = (x_1, x_2), y = (y_1, y_2).$$

$$(i) \text{ If } x = y, \text{ then } d(x, x) = |x_1 - x_1| + |x_2 - x_2| = 0.$$

$$\text{If } x \neq y, \text{ then } d(x, y) = |x_1 - y_1| + |x_2 - y_2| > 0.$$

$$(ii) \quad \begin{aligned} d(x, y) &= |x_1 - y_1| + |x_2 - y_2| \\ &= |-(y_1 - x_1)| + |-(y_2 - x_2)| \\ &= |y_1 - x_1| + |y_2 - x_2| \\ &= d(y, x). \end{aligned}$$

$$(iii) \quad \begin{aligned} d(x, y) &= |x_1 - y_1| + |x_2 - y_2| \\ &= |x_1 - z_1 + z_1 - y_1| + |x_2 - z_2 + z_2 - y_2| \\ &\leq |x_1 - z_1| + |z_1 - y_1| + |x_2 - z_2| + |z_2 - y_2| \\ &= (|x_1 - z_1| + |x_2 - z_2|) + (|z_1 - y_1| + |z_2 - y_2|) \\ &= d(x, z) + d(z, y). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $d(x, y) = |x_1 - y_1| + |x_2 - y_2|$ is a metric space on $\mathbb{R}^2$.

2.3 Definitions. Let X be a metric space and $E \subseteq X$.

A *neighbourhood of a point p* is a set $N_r(p)$ consisting of all points q such that $d(p, q) < r$.

The number r is called the *radius* of $N_r(p)$.

A point p is a *limit point* of the set E if every neighbourhood of p contains a point $q \neq p$ such that $q \in E$.

E is *closed* if every limit point of E is a point of E .

A point p is an *interior point* of E if there is a neighbourhood N of p such that $N \subseteq E$.

E is **open** if every point of E is an interior point of E .

The **complement of E** (denoted by E^c) is the set of all points $p \in X$ such that $p \notin E$.

E is **bounded** if there is a real number M and a point $q \in X$ such that $d(p, q) < M$ for all $p \in E$.

2.4 Theorem. Every neighbourhood is an open set.

Proof. Let $E = N_r(p)$ be a neighbourhood of a point p with radius r .

Let q be any point of E .

Then $d(p, q) < r$.

Let $h = r - d(p, q) > 0$.

Then $d(p, q) = r - h$.

For all points s such that $d(q, s) < h$, then

$$d(p, s) \leq d(p, q) + d(q, s)$$

$$< r - h + h$$

$$= r.$$

So $s \in N_r(p) = E$.

Thus q is an interior point of E .

Hence E is open. $\square$

2.5 Theorem. A set E is open if and only if its complement is closed.

Proof. First, suppose E^c is closed.

Let x be an element in E .

Then $x \notin E^c$ and so x is not a limit point of E^c .

Hence there exists a neighbourhood N of x such that $E^c \cap N$ is empty.

That is, $N \subset E$.

So x is an interior point of E .

Hence E is open.

Next, suppose E is open.

Let x be a limit point of E^c .

Then every neighbourhood of x contains a point of E^c .

So x is not an interior point of E .

Since E is open, $x \notin E$.

Thus $x \in E^c$.

Hence E^c is closed. $\square$

2.6 Theorem. If f is a continuous mapping of a compact metric space X into R^k , then $f(X)$ is closed and bounded. Thus, f is bounded.

Proof. Let f be a continuous mapping of a compact metric space X into R^k .

$f(X)$ is compact in R^k .

$f(X)$ is closed and bounded.

Next to prove f is bounded.

Let $x \in X$ and $f(x) = (f_1(x), \dots, f_k(x))$.

Since $f(X)$ is bounded, $\exists N \in R, \exists y = (y_1, \dots, y_k) \in R^k$ such that $|f(x) - y| < N$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } |f_i(x) - y_i| &\leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^k |f_i(x) - y_i|^2 \right)^{1/2} \\ &= |f(x) - y| < N. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $-N < f_i(x) - y_i < N$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$.

Thus $-N + y_i < f_i(x) < N + y_i = M$ (say), so that

$$-M < f_i(x) < M \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, k.$$

$$\text{Thus } |f(x)| = \left(\sum_{i=1}^k (f_i(x))^2 \right)^{1/2} < (kM^2)^{1/2}.$$

That is, $|f(x)| \leq L$ for all $x \in X$.

Hence f is bounded. $\square$

2.7 Definitions. An *open cover* of a set E in a metric space X is a collection $\{G_\alpha\}$ of open subsets of X such that $E \subseteq \bigcup_\alpha G_\alpha$.

A subset K of a metric space X is said to be *compact* if every open cover of K contains a finite subcover.

2.8 Theorem. Compact subsets of metric spaces are closed.

Proof. Let K be a compact subset of a metric space.

Suppose $p \in X, p \notin K$.

If $q \in K$, let V_q and W_q be neighbourhoods of p and q , respectively, of radius less than

$$\frac{1}{2}d(p, q).$$

Since K is compact, there are finitely many points $q_1, \dots, q_n$ in K such that

$$K \subseteq W_{q_1} \cup \dots \cup W_{q_n} = W.$$

If $V = V_{q_1} \cap \dots \cap V_{q_n}$, then V is a neighbourhood of p which does not intersect W .

Hence $V \subseteq K^c$, so that p is an interior point of K^c .

Thus K^c is open.

Hence K is closed. $\square$

2.9 Theorem. Closed subsets of compact sets are compact.

Proof. Suppose $F \subset K \subset X$, F is closed (relative to X), and K is compact.

Let $\{V_\alpha\}$ be an open cover of E .

If F^c is adjoined to $\{V_\alpha\}$, we obtain an open cover Ω of K .

Since K is compact, there is a finite collection Φ of Ω which covers K , and hence F .

That is, $F \subset V_{\alpha_1} \cup \dots \cup V_{\alpha_n}$.

If F^c is a member of Φ , we may remove from Φ and still retain an open cover of F .

Thus a finite subcollection of $\{V_\alpha\}$ covers F .

Hence F is compact. $\square$

2.10 Definitions. Suppose X and Y are two metric spaces, $E \subset X$, $p \in E$ and f maps E into Y .

Then f is said to be **continuous at p** if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists a $\delta > 0$ such that $d_Y(f(x), f(p)) < \varepsilon$ for all points $x \in E$ for which $d_X(x, p) < \delta$.

If f is continuous at every point of E , then f is said to be **continuous on E** .

2.11 Theorem. Suppose f is a continuous mapping of a compact metric space X into a metric space Y . Then $f(X)$ is compact.

Proof. Let $\{V_\alpha\}$ be an open cover of $f(X)$. Since f is continuous, each of the sets $f^{-1}(V_\alpha)$ is open.

Since X is compact, there are infinitely many indices $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ such that

$X \subset f^{-1}(V_{\alpha_1}) \cup \dots \cup f^{-1}(V_{\alpha_n})$.

Since $f(f^{-1}(E)) \subset E$ for $E \subset Y$, implies that $f(X) \subset V_{\alpha_1} \cup \dots \cup V_{\alpha_n}$.

Hence $f(X)$ is compact. $\square$

2.12 Theorem. Suppose f is a continuous 1-1 mapping of a compact metric space X onto a metric space Y . Then the inverse mapping f^{-1} is defined on Y by $f^{-1}(f(x)) = x$ ($x \in X$) is a continuous mapping of Y onto X .

Proof. A mapping f of a metric space X onto a metric space Y is continuous on X if and only if $f^{-1}(V)$ is open in X for every open set V in Y .

It is sufficient to prove that $f(V)$ is open set in Y for every open set V in X .

Fix such a set V .

Then the complement V^c of V is closed in X .

Hence V^c is compact, since X is compact, and a closed subset of a compact set is compact.

Hence $f(V^c)$ is a compact subset of Y and so $f(V^c)$ is closed in Y .

Since f is one-one and onto, $f(V)$ is the complement of $f(V^c)$.

Hence $f(V)$ is open. $\square$

Conclusion

In this paper, mathematical analysis is the branch of mathematics dealing with limit and related theories such as differentiation, integration, measure, infinite series, and analytic function. These theories are usually studied in the context of real and complex numbers and function. Analysis evolved from calculus, which involves the elementary concepts and techniques of analysis. Analysis may be distinguished from geometry; however, it can be applied to any space of mathematical objects that has definition of nearness (a topological space) or special distance between objects (a metric space). Much of analysis happens in some metric space; the most commonly used are the real line, the complex plane, Euclidean space, other vector spaces, and the integers. Examples of analysis without a metric include measure theory (which describes size rather than distance) and functional analysis.

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